

GENERAL THEORY FOR THE MODELLING OF LAMINATED MULTI-LAYER PLATES AND ITS APPLICATION FOR THE ANALYSIS OF SANDWICH PANELS WITH PLY DROPS

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SUMMARY: Multi-layer sandwich type structures can be identified in many structural assemblies involving composite materials. These multi-layer composite assemblies are characterised by having interchanging layers of high density and high stiffness separated by low density and compliant interface layers. A characteristic feature of such multi-layer assemblies is that severe and highly localised stress concentrations appear under certain conditions. The quantitative understanding of these phenomena involves a detailed description of the complicated mechanical interaction of the stiff layers through the compliant interface layers. The paper presents a high-order plate theory formulation, which inherently includes a description of the global response as well as the local responses of the individual layers of an arbitrary multiple layer structural plate assembly. The features of the high-order multi-layer plate theory are demonstrated through analysis of the elastic response of a CFRP/honeycomb cored sandwich panel with symmetric exterior ply drops.

KEYWORDS: multi-layer plates, sandwich type structures, stiff solid laminates, compliant interface layers, high-order plate theory, discontinuities, terminating plies, ply drops.

INTRODUCTION

Multi-layer sandwich type structures can be identified in many structural assemblies involving composite materials. Such multi-layer composite assemblies are characterised by having interchanging high stiffness layers separated by low stiffness interface layers. The simplest example of such a layered composite assembly is the classical sandwich configuration, where two stiff face sheets are separated by a low stiffness core material. Another example is a composite laminate consisting of an arbitrary number of plies, where distinct interface layers can be identified. A characteristic feature of such multi-layer assemblies is that severe and strongly localised stress concentrations appear under certain conditions, where the stiff layers interact through the compliant interface layers. A well known example of this is the free edge

problem known from composite laminates (N stiff layers and $(N-1)$ compliant interface layers). The understanding of these phenomena involves a detailed description of the complicated interaction between the stiff layers through the compliant interface layers.

There are several suggestions for the development of theories of varying order for the analysis of multi-layer plates. The simplest approach is to use the classical laminate theory (CST) based on the Love-Kirchhoff assumptions, as described in [1]. This theory does not account for interlaminar and transverse shearing effects, but these can be included by adopting high-order theories, as discussed by among others Reddy [2] and Savoia et al. [3], in which high-order displacement fields are assumed across the thickness of the laminated assemblies. A special high-order formulation for the analysis of symmetric sandwich plates (3 layer assembly) is suggested by Librescu [4], including the presence of transverse normal stresses in the core material. None of the quoted references include the transverse flexibility, however, thus ignoring the effects associated with changes of the laminate thickness.

The present paper presents a high-order multi-layer plate theory, which inherently includes a description of the global response as well as the local responses of the individual layers of an arbitrary multi-layer structural assembly. The theory includes the transverse flexibility of the interface layers in the modelling.

FORMULATION OF HIGH-ORDER MULTI-LAYER PLATE THEORY

The “high-order” theory concept adopted in this paper was originally introduced by Frostig et al. [5-7], for 3-layer sandwich beams, and by Thomsen and Rits [8], Thomsen [9] for 3-layer sandwich plates. The ideas behind these high-order sandwich theories are extended to multi-layer plate configurations as defined by Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Geometrical definition of multi-layer plate element consisting of N high stiffness solid laminates and $(N-1)$ compliant interface/core layers.

Basic Assumptions

With reference to Fig. 1 the high-order plate theory includes the following features:

- The multi-layer plate consists of N high stiffness and high strength layers separated by $(N-1)$ interface layers of low stiffness.

- The N high stiffness layers, denoted as solid laminates, are modelled as generally orthotropic laminated plates adopting the classical Love-Kirchhoff assumptions.
- The $(N-1)$ low stiffness or compliant interface layers are modelled as a special type of orthotropic solid, only possessing stiffness in the out-of-plane direction. Accordingly, the in-plane stresses are assumed to be nil in the interface layers, while transverse shear and transverse normal stresses are accounted for.

Modelling of Solid Laminates:

For the purposes of the present paper, the general plate theory out-lined above is shown for the special case of cylindrical bending. With reference to Fig. 1, cylindrical bending is defined as a state of deformation where the fundamental variables are functions of the longitudinal coordinate x alone. Consequently, the displacement field is uniform in the width direction (y), and can be described as follows:

$$u_0^i = u_0^i(x), \quad v_0^i = v_0^i(x), \quad w^i = w^i(x) \quad (1)$$

where u_0^i , v_0^i and w^i are the middle plane displacements in the x , y and z directions, respectively, and i refers to the i 'th solid laminate of the multi-layer plate ($i=1, \dots, N$). As a consequence of Eqn 1, the following is deduced:

$$u_{0,y}^i = v_{0,y}^i = w_{,y}^i = w_{,yy}^i = 0 \quad (2)$$

where differentiation with respect to the spatial coordinates is represented by a subscript comma. It should be noted that the concept of cylindrical bending is not unique, and that other definitions than the one used in the present formulation can be adopted, Ref. 1. According to the Love-Kirchhoff assumptions, and by adopting Eqn 2, the kinematic relations for the i 'th solid laminate ($i=1, \dots, N$) are expressed as

$$u^i = u_0^i + z\beta_x^i, \quad \beta_x^i = -w_{,x}^i, \quad v^i = v_0^i + z\beta_y^i, \quad \beta_y^i = -w_{,x}^i = 0 \quad (3)$$

Substitution of Eqn 2 into the general constitutive relations for a laminated generally orthotropic plate yields the constitutive relations for the i 'th solid laminate ($i=1, \dots, N$) in a state of cylindrical bending:

$$\begin{aligned} N_{xx}^i &= A_{11}^i u_{0,x}^i + A_{16}^i v_{0,x}^i - B_{11}^i w_{,xx}^i, & M_{xx}^i &= B_{11}^i u_{0,x}^i + B_{16}^i v_{0,x}^i - D_{11}^i w_{,xx}^i \\ N_{yy}^i &= A_{12}^i u_{0,x}^i + A_{26}^i v_{0,x}^i - B_{12}^i w_{,xx}^i, & M_{yy}^i &= B_{12}^i u_{0,x}^i + B_{26}^i v_{0,x}^i - D_{12}^i w_{,xx}^i \\ N_{xy}^i &= A_{16}^i u_{0,x}^i + A_{66}^i v_{0,x}^i - B_{16}^i w_{,xx}^i, & M_{xy}^i &= B_{16}^i u_{0,x}^i + B_{66}^i v_{0,x}^i - D_{16}^i w_{,xx}^i \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where A_{jk}^i , B_{jk}^i , D_{jk}^i ($j,k=1,2,6$) are the extensional, coupling and bending stiffnesses of the i 'th solid laminate. N_{xx}^i , N_{yy}^i , N_{xy}^i are the in-plane stress resultants, and M_{xx}^i , M_{yy}^i , M_{xy}^i are the moment resultants of the i 'th solid laminate.

With reference to Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, the equilibrium equations for the i 'th solid laminate for the case of cylindrical bending (i.e. all derivatives with respect to y vanish) are given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
N_{xx,x}^i &= \tau_{zx}^i - \tau_{zx}^{i-1}, & N_{xy,x}^i &= \tau_{zy}^i - \tau_{zy}^{i-1}, & Q_{x,x}^i &= \sigma_z^{i(top)} - \sigma_z^{i-1(bottom)} \\
M_{xx,x}^i &= Q_x^i - \frac{f_i}{2} \{ \tau_{zx}^i + \tau_{zx}^{i-1} \}, & M_{xy,x}^i &= Q_y^i - \frac{f_i}{2} \{ \tau_{zy}^i + \tau_{zy}^{i-1} \}
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where τ_{zx}^i, τ_{zy}^i are the shear stress components in the i 'th interface layer, $\sigma_z^{i(top)}$ is the transverse normal stress component along the boundary between the i 'th solid laminate and the i 'th interface layer (i.e. the *top* boundary of the i 'th interface layer), $\sigma_z^{i-1(bottom)}$ is the transverse normal stress component along the boundary between the i 'th solid laminate and the $(i-1)$ 'th interface layer (i.e. the *bottom* interface of the $(i-1)$ 'th interface layer), f_i is the thickness of the i 'th solid laminate, and Q_x^i, Q_y^i are the transverse shear stress resultants in the i 'th solid laminate.

Fig. 2: Equilibrium conditions for the i 'th solid laminate.

Modelling of Interface Layers

As mentioned, the $(N-1)$ compliant interface layers are modelled as a special type of orthotropic linear elastic solid, only possessing stiffness in the out-of-plane direction (z). Consequently, the stiffness properties of the i 'th interface layer are characterised by the transverse Young's modulus E_{cz}^i and the two transverse shear moduli G_{cxz}^i and G_{cyz}^i . As a consequence of the assumed zero in-plane stiffness the in-plane stresses are nil, and the stress field in the i 'th interface layer is described solely by the transverse normal stress component σ_z^i and the two transverse shear stress components τ_{xz}^i, τ_{yz}^i .

Combination of the interface layer equilibrium equations with the interface layer kinematic and constitutive relations yields a set of equations, which describes the complete interface layer stress and displacement fields in terms of the transverse coordinate z (measured from the middle plane of each interface layer, see Fig. 1), and in terms of the solid laminate displacement components. The response of the i 'th interface layer is coupled with the responses of the surrounding solid laminates (i.e. solid laminates $(i+1)$ and i , see Fig. 1) by requiring continuity of the displacements across the solid laminate/interface layer boundaries. This implies that the solid laminates and the interface layers interact through the transfer of surface tractions and shear stresses. For the special case of cylindrical bending the resulting interface layer field equations read:

$$\begin{aligned}
\tau_{xz}^i(x, y, z) &= \tau_{xz}^i(x), \quad \tau_{yz}^i(x, y, z) = \tau_{yz}^i(x), \quad \sigma_z^i(x, y, z) = \sigma_z^i(x, z) = \frac{E_{cz}^i}{c_i} \{w^i - w^{i+1}\} - \tau_{xz,x}^i z \\
w_c^i(x, y, z) &= w_c^i(x, z) = w^i + \frac{\{w^i - w^{i+1}\}}{c_i} \left\{z - \frac{c_i}{2}\right\} - \frac{1}{2E_{cz}^i} \tau_{xz,x}^i \left\{z^2 - \frac{(c_i)^2}{4}\right\} \\
u_c^i(x, y, z) &= u_c^i(x, z) = u_0^i + \frac{w_{,x}^i}{2} \left\{f_i - \frac{z^2}{c_i} - z + \frac{3c_i}{4}\right\} + \frac{w_{,x}^{i+1}}{2} \left\{\frac{z^2}{c_i} - z + \frac{c_i}{4}\right\} + \frac{\tau_{xz}^i}{G_{cxz}^i} \left\{z - \frac{c_i}{2}\right\} \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2E_{cz}^i} \tau_{xz,xx}^i \left\{\frac{z^3}{3} - \frac{(c_i)^2 z}{4} + \frac{(c_i)^3}{12}\right\} \\
v_c^i(x, y, z) &= v_c^i(x, z) = v_0^i + \frac{\tau_{yz}^i}{G_{cyz}^i} \left\{z - \frac{c_i}{2}\right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where u_c^i, v_c^i, w_c^i are the in-plane and out-of-plane displacements, and c_i is the thickness of the i 'th interface layer. From Eqn 6 it is observed that τ_{xz}^i and τ_{yz}^i are constant, that σ_z^i varies linearly, that w_c^i varies quadratically, that u_c^i varies cubically and that v_c^i varies linearly across the thickness of the i 'th interface layer.

Complete Set of Governing Equations

Combination of the solid laminate equations, Eqn 1-5, with the interface layer equations, Eqn 6, yields the complete set of governing differential equations for the i 'th solid laminate and the i 'th interface layer. For the case of cylindrical bending, where all the fundamental variables are functions of x alone, the governing equations can be expressed in the form:

i 'th solid laminate:

$$\begin{aligned}
u_{0,x}^i &= \alpha_1^i N_{xx}^i + \alpha_2^i N_{xy}^i + \alpha_3^i M_{xx}^i, \quad v_{0,x}^i = \alpha_4^i N_{xx}^i + \alpha_5^i N_{xy}^i + \alpha_6^i M_{xx}^i \\
w_{,x}^i &= -\beta_x^i, \quad \beta_{x,x}^i = \alpha_7^i N_{xx}^i + \alpha_8^i N_{xy}^i + \alpha_9^i M_{xx}^i \\
N_{xx,x}^i &= -\{\tau_{zx}^{i-1} - \tau_{zx}^i\}, \quad N_{xy,x}^i = -\{\tau_{zy}^{i-1} - \tau_{zy}^i\}, \quad M_{xx,x}^i = Q_x^i - \frac{f_i}{2} \{\tau_{zx}^{i-1} + \tau_{zx}^i\} \\
Q_{x,x}^i &= -w^{i-1} \frac{E_{cz}^{i-1}}{c_{i-1}} - q_x^{i-1} \frac{c_{i-1}}{2} + w^i \left\{ \frac{E_{cz}^{i-1}}{c_{i-1}} + \frac{E_{cz}^i}{c_i} \right\} - q_x^i \frac{c_i}{2} - w^{i+1} \frac{E_{cz}^i}{c_i}
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

i 'th interface layer:

$$\begin{aligned}
\tau_{xz,x}^i &= q_x^i, \quad \tau_{yz,x}^i = q_y^i \\
q_{x,x}^i &= \frac{12E_{cz}^i}{(c_i)^3} \left\{ -u_0^i + \frac{(f_i + c_i)}{2} \beta_x^i + u_0^{i+1} + \frac{(f_{i+1} + c_i)}{2} \beta_x^{i+1} + \frac{c_i}{G_{cxz}^i} \tau_{xz}^i \right\} \\
q_{y,x}^i &= \frac{G_{cyz}^i}{c_i} \left\{ k_7^i Q_x^i + k_8^i \tau_{xz}^{i-1} + \langle k_9^i - k_8^{i+1} \rangle \tau_{xz}^i - k_9^{i+1} \tau_{xz}^{i+1} \right. \\
&\quad \left. - k_3^i \tau_{yz}^{i-1} + \langle k_3^i + k_3^{i+1} \rangle \tau_{yz}^i - k_3^{i+1} \tau_{yz}^{i+1} - k_7^{i+1} Q_x^{i+1} \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where α_m^i ($m=1-7$) and k_m^i ($m=3$ and $7-9$) are coefficients determined from the solid laminate extensional, coupling and bending stiffnesses $A_{mn}^i, B_{mn}^i, D_{mn}^i$ ($m, n=1, 2, 6$). For the i 'th solid laminate interface layer the solution vectors containing the fundamental variables defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} & \{u_0^i, v_0^i, w^i, \beta_x^i, N_{xx}^i, N_{xy}^i, M_{xx}^i, Q_x^i\} \quad i = 1, \dots, N \\ & \{\tau_{xz}^i, \tau_{yz}^i, q_x^i, q_y^i\} \quad i = 1, \dots, N-1 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

are determined from the solution of the field equations, Eqn 7, 8. When the solution given by Eqn 9 has been obtained, the following solid laminate quantities can be determined directly from the constitutive relations, Eqn 4, and the equilibrium equations, Eqn 5:

$$\{N_{yy}^i, M_{yy}^i, M_{xy}^i, Q_y^i\} \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (10)$$

In addition the interface layer quantities

$$\{u_c^i, v_c^i, w_c^i, \sigma_z^i\} \quad i = 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (11)$$

can be determined from Eqn 6. The quantities given by Eqn 10 can be physically interpreted as the stress and moment resultants, which have to be applied along the edges $y=\text{constant}$ in order to maintain a state of cylindrical bending in the multi-layer plate.

Multi-segment Method of Integration

For an arbitrary multi-layer plate, composed of N solid laminates, and $(N-1)$ compliant interface layers, the order of the set of governing equations is $N \times 8 + (N-1) \times 4$, since the necessary number of boundary conditions to be specified along an edge $x=\text{constant}$ exactly equals half this number. The governing equations, Eqn 7, 8, together with the statement of the boundary conditions, constitute a multiple point boundary value problem, which in the present investigation has been solved numerically using the multi-segment method of integration. This method is based on a transformation of the original multiple point boundary value problem into a series of interconnected initial value problems. The considered multi-layer plate configuration is divided into a finite number of segments, and the solution within each segment is derived by direct integration. Continuity of the solution vectors across the separation points between the segments, as well as fulfilment of the boundary conditions is ensured by formulating and solving a set of linear algebraic equations.

EXAMPLE: CFRP/HONEYCOMB CORED SANDWICH PANEL WITH EXTERIOR PLY DROPS

The developed high-order multi-layer plate theory enables the prediction of the mechanical response characteristics displayed by a number of complicated structural problems including: ply drop effects and free edge effects in composite laminates, adhesive bonded joints, multi-layer sandwich plates and many other problems involving layered structural assemblies. In this paper the capabilities of the theory are demonstrated through analysis of a CFRP/honeycomb cored sandwich panel with exterior ply drops placed symmetrically on each side, as shown schematically in Fig. 3. Fig. 3 illustrates a simplified version of an important practical problem, since the thickness of composite sandwich panel face sheets is often increased locally in order to provide for the load transfer around highly loaded locations such as joints, rivets, bolts or inserts. Usually plies are dropped internally, but exterior ply drops are also used quite frequently. At the stations where ply drops are made, the local bending stiffness of

the face laminates changes discontinuously, thus inducing severe local bending effects. These local bending effects induce severe stress concentrations, which may initiate delamination, core crushing or solid laminate bending failure [10-12].

Fig. 3: CFRP/honeycomb cored sandwich panel with exterior ply drops.

With reference to Fig. 1 and Fig. 3, the sandwich plate configuration is composed of a 3-layer structural assembly for $0 \leq x \leq L_1$ and a 7-layer assembly for $L_1 \leq x \leq L_1 + L_2$:

- Solid laminates: 5245C T-800 from Narmco/BASF; toughened carbon (T-800 fibres)/bismaleimide prepreg system: $E_{11}=165$ GPa, $E_{22}=9.7$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.31$, $G_{12}=4.8$ GPa, cured ply thickness=0.152 mm [12].
- Interface layers 1 & 3: Prepreg bismaleimide resin: $E_z=3.3$ GPa, $G_{xz}=G_{yz}=1.2$ GPa [12].
- Interface layer 2: Aluminium honeycomb; Hexcel 3/16"-5052-0.001": $E_z=517$ MPa, $G_{xz}=310$ MPa, $G_{yz}=152$ MPa [12].
- Stacking sequences: Laminate 2 & 3: $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$. Laminate 1: $[90^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ]$. Laminate 4: $[-45^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ]$. The quoted stacking sequences are counted from the top and downwards.
- Geometry: $L_1=L_2=25$ mm, $f_i=0.456$ mm ($i=1-4$), $c_1=c_3=0.1$ mm, $c_2=10$ mm.
- Boundary conditions: As shown in Fig. 3.
- External load: $x=0: N_{xx}^2=N_{xx}^3=P/2$, $P=100$ N/mm.

The analysed configuration is geometrically symmetric about the middle plane of interface layer 2 (the sandwich core), but solid laminates 1 and 4 (dropped sub laminates) are stacked asymmetrically with respect to their own middle planes as well as with respect to the middle plane of interface layer 2. Consequently, the mechanical response will display coupling effects including non-zero width direction displacements (v_0^i , v_c^i), non-zero width direction interface layer shear stresses (τ_{yz}^i), and non-zero in-plane shear stress and twist moment resultants (N_{xy}^i , M_{xy}^i) in the solid laminates.

Fig. 4 shows the predicted displacements, and it is observed from the distribution of w^i that severe local bending effects are induced near the ply drop position at $x=L_1=25$ mm. In particular it is noticed that the dropped laminates ($i=1$ and 4) tends to peel of solid laminates 2 and 3, thus indicating the presence of tensile transverse normal stresses (peeling stresses) in interface layers 1 and 3. Non-zero width direction displacements v_0^i are also seen, as expected due to the asymmetric stacking of the dropped laminates 1 and 4.

Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 display the predicted interface layer stresses, which have been normalised with respect to the nominal stress in solid laminates 2 and 3 at $x=0$ (point of load introduction):

$$\sigma_{nom} = \frac{N_{xx}^2}{f_2} = \frac{N_{xx}^3}{f_3} = \frac{P}{2f_2} = 109.6 \text{ MPa} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 4: Solid laminate displacements $u_0^i(x)$, $v_0^i(x)$, $w^i(x)$; $i=1-4$.

Fig. 5: Normalised interface layer transverse normal stresses along the boundaries to the solid laminates.

Fig. 5 shows the transverse normal stresses along the top ($\sigma_z^{i(top)}$) and bottom ($\sigma_z^{i(bottom)}$) boundaries between the interface layers and the solid laminates. According to Eqn 6 the variation of the transverse normal stresses across the interface layers is linear, and it is seen that this variation is very large close to the free edge at $x=L_1=25$ mm of interface layers 1 and 3. Thus, very large tensile interface layer transverse normal stresses are induced along the most remote boundary relative to the middle plane of the complete sandwich panel, whereas large compressive transverse normal stresses are induced along the boundary closest to the sandwich panel middle plane. It is further seen that the presence of transverse normal stresses in interface layers 1 and 3 is very localised, and a complete decay is observed a few interface layer thicknesses from the ply drop position. The transverse normal stresses in the core material (interface layer 2) are very small compared with the stresses in interface layers 1 and

3. The values obtained for the top and bottom interfaces of interface layer 2 are identical, and follow a pattern, which is identical to the out-of plane displacements of solid laminates 2 and 3, see Fig. 4. This indicates that the core material acts as a simple elastic foundation.

Fig. 6: Normalised interface layer shear stresses (core stresses τ_{xz}^2 and τ_{yz}^2 are not shown since they are negligibly small).

Fig. 6 shows the distribution of normalised shear stresses in interface layers 1 and 3, and the shear stresses are constant across the interface layers according to Eqn 6. Non-zero shear stresses are also predicted for the core layer (interface layer 2), but these are not shown, since they are very small compared with the other shear stress components. The longitudinal shear stresses in interface layers 1 and 3 (τ_{xz}^1 , τ_{xz}^3) are of equal magnitude but of opposite signs, and the imposed free edge conditions of zero shear stresses at the ply drop position, $x=L_1=25$ mm, are fulfilled. The peak values of τ_{xz}^1 , τ_{xz}^3 are obtained a few interface layer thicknesses from the ply drop position. The interface layer shear stresses in the width direction, i.e. τ_{yz}^1 , τ_{yz}^3 , are also shown in Fig. 6, and it is observed that they are small compared with τ_{xz}^1 , τ_{xz}^3 .

The elastic response of the CFRP/sandwich panel with ply drops also includes severe stress concentrations in the solid laminates. These stress concentrations are associated with the localised bending phenomena shown in Fig. 4, but no further results will be presented herein.

CONCLUSIONS

A high-order multi-layer plate theory has been presented. The theory inherently includes a description of the global response, as well as the local responses of the individual layers, of an arbitrary multi-layer plate assembly, where N high stiffness layers are separated by $(N-1)$ compliant interface layers. The theory includes the transverse flexibility of the interface layers, thus allowing the thickness of the complete multi-layer plate assembly to change during deformation. The theory provides a complete solution with respect to the displacements, stress resultants and moment resultants of the solid laminates, as well as the displacements, transverse normal stresses and shear stresses of the interface layers.

The high-order multi-layer plate theory can be used for the analysis of the mechanical response displayed by a number of complicated structural problems involving multi-layer assemblies. In the present paper the features of the theory has been demonstrated through

analysis of the elastic response of a CFRP/honeycomb cored sandwich panel with exterior ply drops. For this particular example, it has been demonstrated that the theory enables the prediction of very complicated load transfer mechanisms, including the interaction of the solid laminates (sandwich face sheets and dropped sub laminates) through the compliant interface and core layers.

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